

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

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ABSTRACT: The growing number of beauty products emerging in the market has intensified competition in the beauty industry. One of the promotional strategies employed to market these products is the use of NCT Dream as brand ambassadors for Somethinc, aiming to enhance brand image and consumer purchase intention. This study aims to examine the direct and indirect influence of NCT Dream as brand ambassadors through TikTok @Somethincofficial on brand image and consumer purchase intention. The concepts used in this study include brand ambassador, brand image, and purchase intention. A quantitative approach with an explanatory research design was employed. The unit of analysis comprises individuals who follow the TikTok account @Somethincofficial. The sampling technique applied was probability sampling using a systematic random sampling method, resulting in 400 respondents who completed a questionnaire distributed via Google Form. The data analysis technique used was path analysis through simple linear regression. The findings indicate that brand ambassadors have a significant influence on brand image, a significant influence on purchase intention, and that brand image also significantly affects purchase intention. The path analysis reveals that the direct effect of the brand ambassador on purchase intention is greater than the indirect effect mediated by brand image. Thus, the presence of brand ambassadors plays a key role in increasing consumer purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Brand Ambassador, Brand Image, Purchase Intention, TikTok Marketing, NCT Dream

INTRODUCTION

Following the COVID-19 pandemic, the cosmetics industry in Indonesia has continued to grow, making it one of the leading sectors in the national economy. Given the large market share, a wide opportunity is available for domestic industry players (Indonesia.go.id, 2024). This is evidenced by the rapid growth of the beauty industry, in line with increasing public awareness regarding the importance of self-care. According to data on beauty industry trends, the average individual uses 4–5 makeup products daily (GoodStats, 2024). Approximately 79% of individuals feel more confident when appearing in public while wearing cosmetics. In addition to beauty products, there is also a growing market for body care, skincare, and other products such as soaps for sensitive or congenital skin conditions (Geni & Budiyantri, 2024).

In Indonesia, the vast market potential of the beauty industry is supported by a significant number of entrepreneurs and the availability of raw materials. By 2024, the market value of Indonesia's beauty industry is projected to reach IDR 146 trillion, with an estimated 100,400 salons, 5,000 barbershops, and 3.97 million retail units distributing beauty and personal care products (Geni & Budiyantri, 2024). Consumers are increasingly aware of the ingredients used in cosmetics and body care, leading many to switch to natural beauty products. This shift is not only due to quality and safety concerns but also due to environmental considerations (Nawiyah et al., 2023). Additionally, from 2024 to 2028, Indonesia's cosmetics industry is expected to grow at an average annual rate of 5.35% (Indonesia.go.id, 2024).

On the other hand, society is becoming more aware of the importance of skincare. According to BPOM, between 2021 and July 2022, the number of cosmetic companies increased from 819 to 913—a growth of 20.6% (Investor.id, 2022). This surge has led to the strengthening of both domestic and international cosmetic brands, offering consumers a wider variety of alternatives when purchasing products (Oktaviani & Estaswara, 2022).

Census data (2020) revealed that Indonesia's population stands at 270.2 million, with 133.5 million women—70% of whom are of productive age (15–64 years) (Kominfo, 2021). Both global and local cosmetic producers are competing to develop new products with innovative brands and categories. One such local brand is Somethinc.

Somethinc is a local beauty brand produced by PT Royal Pesona Indonesia, founded in March 2019 by Irene Ursula, who is also the founder of the Indonesian beauty platform Beautyhaul. The founder was inspired to launch Somethinc due to the lack of high-quality cosmetic products. PT Royal Pesona Indonesia, established in 2014 by Irene Ursula, Benny Yahya, and Marsela Limesa, is the first beauty e-commerce platform in Indonesia, launching various beauty brands including Somethinc (idntimes, 2024).

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

A survey by Populix in 2022 showed that the most widely used cosmetics brand was Wardah (48%), followed by Emina (40%) and Make Over (22%). In comparison, Somethinc was used by only 19% of Indonesian consumers. To improve sales and emerge as a leading brand in the highly competitive Indonesian beauty market, Somethinc is leveraging the trending Korean Wave phenomenon (Puspitasari et al., 2023).

The Korean Wave, or Hallyu, has become popular in many countries. South Korea continues to expand its cultural influence globally, including in Indonesia. Initially popular in East Asia, the Korean Wave is now recognized worldwide (Jin, 2016; Shim, 2006). Various elements of Korean culture—dramas, films, music, TV shows, cultural festivals, cuisine, electronics, fashion, speech styles, language, and even cosmetics—have become familiar to Indonesian society (Sarajwati, 2020; Visser, 2002).

The Korean Wave, especially popular among youth, has influenced the millennial generation. Indonesia is home to millions of K-pop fans. According to 2021 Twitter data compiled by GoodStats, Indonesia ranks as the country with the largest number of K-pop fans globally. Indonesian youth are particularly fond of K-pop and K-dramas, subconsciously absorbing various elements of Korean culture.

Furthermore, the Korean Wave has had a significant impact on beauty trends in Indonesia. K-Beauty, which emphasizes natural and healthy skin aesthetics, has become a major trend. K-Beauty products, often promoted by Korean celebrities as brand ambassadors, have become popular choices among Indonesian women (Nabilah & Yunanto, 2024).

Local cosmetic companies in Indonesia have begun adopting Korean beauty trends by focusing on natural ingredients for youthful and healthy skin. In addition to quality, many local brands collaborate with Korean celebrities, particularly K-pop idols, to attract fans. One such marketing strategy is the appointment of Korean boyband NCT Dream as brand ambassadors for Somethinc, recognizing Indonesia as the country with the largest K-pop fanbase (Alifah, 2022).

According to Royan (2005), advertisements featuring popular celebrities can influence the public perception of products and boost sales. Therefore, Somethinc chose NCT Dream as brand ambassadors, considering that brand ambassadors are one of the most effective marketing communication strategies for attracting attention and fostering consumer interest, which in turn influences brand image and consumer purchase intention.

Firmansyah (2019) defines a brand ambassador as a well-known celebrity who has a passion for a particular brand and is employed to influence or persuade consumers to use a product. Similarly, Samosir et al. (2016) describe a brand ambassador as someone appointed to represent a brand or company in promoting a product to increase sales. However, companies must consider various factors when selecting a brand ambassador, as their characteristics can determine the success or failure of promotional efforts.

Lea-Greenwood (2014) identifies five dimensions to measure the effectiveness of brand ambassadors:

1. **Transference** – the alignment of the celebrity's profession with the brand;
2. **Congruence** – the compatibility between the brand and the celebrity;
3. **Credibility** – the extent to which consumers trust the celebrity's message based on relevant knowledge and expertise;
4. **Appeal** – non-physical attractiveness that can influence consumer perception;
5. **Power** – the charisma of the celebrity in influencing consumers to purchase or use the product.

A strong emotional connection between the brand ambassador and consumers can build a positive brand image. According to the American Marketing Association (Keller & Swaminathan, 2020), a brand is a name, term, sign, symbol, or design that identifies a seller's product or service and differentiates it from competitors. A brand can either add to or detract from the value of a product. Consumers typically choose familiar brands due to a sense of security. Firmansyah (2019) defines brand image as the consumer's perception and thoughts upon encountering a brand. A positive brand image increases the likelihood of purchase. In essence, brand image refers to the consumer's belief in a product or service based on brand associations.

Kotler and Keller (2016) propose that brand image can be measured through three key aspects:

1. **Favorability of brand associations** – the extent to which the brand meets consumer needs (e.g., reliability, comfort, and supportive messaging);
2. **Uniqueness of brand associations** – the unique advantages a brand offers that distinguish it from competitors (Keller & Swaminathan, 2020);
3. **Strength of brand associations** – how often and intensely consumers reflect on the product and associate it with existing brand knowledge.

Brand image can influence **purchase intention**, which refers to the likelihood that consumers will switch brands or choose to buy a product (Kotler & Keller, 2016). According to Schiffman and Kanuk (in Priansa, 2017), purchase intention arises when consumers are influenced by product quality, reputation, and information, including strengths and weaknesses compared to competitors.

Ferdinand (2014) identifies four indicators of purchase intention:

1. **Transactional intention** – the desire to purchase a product;
2. **Referential intention** – the tendency to recommend a product to others;
3. **Preferential intention** – a strong preference for a product, though it may change if issues arise;

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

4. **Explorative intention** – the curiosity to seek new information or updates about the product.

Furthermore, research by Molina et al. (2023) found that brand ambassadors significantly influence brand image and purchase intention, with the direct influence being stronger than the indirect one. Similarly, studies by Adingsih and Yunani (2023) confirmed the significant impact of brand ambassadors on both brand image and purchase intention, again with direct effects outweighing indirect ones. In contrast, Adawiyah (2018) found that the indirect effect—mediated by brand image—was stronger than the direct effect.

Based on the literature review and research gap, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H1: There is a direct influence of brand ambassadors on purchase intention.

H2: There is a direct influence of brand ambassadors on brand image.

H3: There is a direct influence of brand image on purchase intention.

H4: There is an indirect influence of brand ambassadors on purchase intention, mediated by brand image.

H5: The direct influence of brand ambassadors on purchase intention is greater than the indirect influence mediated by brand image.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach, which tests objective theories by examining the measurable relationships between variables (Creswell, 2018). Accordingly, the research investigates causal relationships, specifically the effect of the brand ambassador variable on brand image and purchase intention. The type of research is explanatory, which seeks to explain the reasons behind a phenomenon and to build, develop, deepen, or test a theory (Neuman, 2014). Thus, this study aims to explain the influence among the three variables to test the validity of the proposed hypotheses.

The population of this study consists of the 3.3 million followers of the TikTok account @Somethincofficial. The sampling technique used was probability sampling with a systematic random sampling method. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula with a 5% margin of error, resulting in 400 respondents from the total population. A sampling interval of 8,250 was applied and repeated until the target of 400 respondents was reached. Data collection was conducted over 21 days by sending direct messages to the selected followers of @Somethincofficial.

The data analysis technique used was path analysis through simple linear regression to determine both the direct and indirect effects among the variables. The following criteria were used in the linear regression analysis:

- **H₀:** $t\text{-value} < t\text{-table}$ or $\text{significance} > 0.05$
- **H₁:** $t\text{-value} > t\text{-table}$ or $\text{significance} < 0.05$

The validity test results showed that all statement items in the brand ambassador, brand image, and purchase intention variables were valid, as their significance values were less than 0.05. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha. A variable is considered reliable if the alpha value exceeds 0.80 (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The reliability test on data from 400 respondents confirmed that all three variables—brand ambassador, brand image, and purchase intention—were reliable.

Based on the table below, it is stated that all tested statement items were valid, as the significance value (p-value) was less than 0.05.

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

Table 1. Validity Test Results of the Brand Ambassador Variable

Statement	Sig (2-tailed)	Information	Status
1	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
2	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
3	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
4	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
5	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
6	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
7	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
8	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
9	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
10	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
11	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
12	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
13	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
14	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
15	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
16	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
17	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
18	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
19	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
20	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
21	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
22	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
23	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
24	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
25	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
26	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
27	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
28	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
29	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
30	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
31	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
32	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
33	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

Table 2. Validity Test Results of the Brand Image Variable

Statement	Sig (2-tailed)	Information	Status
1	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
2	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
3	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
4	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
5	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
6	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
7	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
8	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
9	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
10	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
11	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
12	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
13	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
14	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
15	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
16	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
17	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
18	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
19	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
20	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

Table 3. Validity Test Results of the Purchase Intention Variable

Statement	Sig (2-tailed)	Information	Status
1	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
2	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
3	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
4	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
5	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
6	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
7	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
8	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
9	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
10	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
11	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
12	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
13	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
14	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
15	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
16	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
17	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
18	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
19	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
20	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
21	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
22	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid
23	0,000	t < 0,05	Valid

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The reliability test for the three variables in this study indicated that they were reliable and consistent, as the Alpha values exceeded 0.80. An Alpha value is considered reliable if it is greater than 0.80 (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Total Items	Alpha Value α	Status
Brand Ambassador	33	0,918	Reliabel
Brand Image	20	0,849	Reliabel
Minat Beli	23	0,894	Reliabel

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Respondents

This study was conducted to examine both the direct and indirect effects of brand ambassadors on purchase intention by distributing questionnaires via Google Forms to respondents who are selected followers of the TikTok account @Somethincofficial. A total of 400 respondents participated in the study, categorized by gender and age.

As shown in **Table 5** below, the majority of respondents were female, accounting for 90%, while the remaining 10% were male. This indicates that Somethinc’s target market is predominantly female, which aligns with the typical interest of women in beauty and skincare products.

Table 5. Respondent Characteristics

Category	Sub-Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	40	10%
	Female	360	90%
Age	< 20 Years	69	17,3%
	20-25 Years	259	64,7%
	>25 Years	72	18%

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The respondents' age distribution shows that 17.3% are under 20 years old, 64.7% or 259 respondents are aged between 20–25 years, and 18% are over 25 years old. It can be concluded that the majority of respondents are in the 20–25 age group. This indicates that NCT Dream shares a similar age range with most of the respondents.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The table below presents the data for the **brand ambassador** variable, which consists of five indicators: transference, congruence, credibility, appeal, and power, comprising a total of 33 statements. Based on the statistical analysis, 77.5% of respondents selected a score of 7, 20.3% selected a score of 6, 1.5% selected a score of 5, and the remaining 0.8% selected a score of 4. These results suggest that the majority of respondents agree with the selection of **NCT Dream** as the brand ambassador for **Somethinc** products.

Table 6. Brand Ambassador Variable

Answer	Frequency	Percentage %
4	3	0,8
5	6	1,5
6	81	20,3
7	310	77,5
Total	100	100

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The table below presents an overview of the **brand image** variable, which consists of three indicators: **favorability**, **uniqueness**, and **strength**, comprising a total of 20 statements. Based on statistical analysis, 74.8% of respondents selected a score of 7, 23.5% selected a score of 6, 1.5% selected a score of 5, and the remaining 0.3% selected a score of 4.

It can therefore be concluded that the majority of respondents agreed that Somethinc’s products are of high quality, offer a unique appeal, and deliver tangible benefits by continuously creating product advantages. These factors contribute to forming a **positive brand image** in the minds of the respondents.

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

Table 7. Brand Image Variable

Answer	Frequency	Percentage %
4	1	0,3
5	6	1,5
6	94	23,5
7	299	74,8
Total	100	100

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The table below presents an overview of the **purchase intention** variable, which consists of four indicators: **transactional**, **referential**, **explorative**, and **preferential**, comprising a total of 23 statements. Based on the statistical analysis, 66.5% of respondents selected a score of 7, 29.5% selected a score of 6, 3.5% selected a score of 5, and the remaining 0.5% selected a score of 4. It can be concluded that the majority of respondents expressed an interest in purchasing Somethinc products. This indicates that the collaboration between Somethinc and NCT Dream has had a **positive impact** in attracting respondents' purchase intention.

Table 8. Purchase Intention Variable

Answer	Frequency	Percentage %
4	2	0,5
5	14	3,5
6	118	29,5
7	266	66,5
Total	100	100

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

The Direct Influence of Brand Ambassador on Purchase Intention

In this study, the first hypothesis tested is the direct influence of the Brand Ambassador on Purchase Intention. The hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H₁: Brand Ambassador has a direct influence on Purchase Intention.

Table 9. Path Coefficient Test Results: Brand Ambassador → Purchase Intention

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	46,540	6,486		7,176	,000
	Brand Ambassador	,450	,033	,530	13,834	,000

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

Based on Table 1, the direct influence of Brand Ambassador on Purchase Intention can be identified. The beta coefficient (β) is 0.530 with a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, **H₁** is accepted, indicating that Brand Ambassador has a direct influence on Purchase Intention.

The Indirect Influence of Brand Ambassador on Purchase Intention

The second hypothesis tested is the indirect influence of Brand Ambassador on Purchase Intention. The research hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H₂: Brand Ambassador has an indirect influence on Purchase Intention.

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

Table 10. Path Coefficient Test Results: Brand Ambassador → Brand Image

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	47,437	4,005		11,843	,000
	Brand Ambassador	,372	,020	,680	18,525	,000

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

a. Dependent Variable: Brand Image

Table 11. Path Coefficient Test Results: Brand Image → Purchase Intention

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	22,582	6,717		3,362	,001
	Brand Image	,934	,055	,647	16,924	,000

Source: Processed by the Researchers, 2024

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

The analysis of indirect influence can be conducted by multiplying the beta coefficients of the direct relationships along the relevant path. In the first stage of the path analysis, as shown in Table 2, the Brand Ambassador variable has a direct influence on Brand Image, with a beta coefficient (β) of 0.680 and a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). In Table 3, the Brand Image variable has a direct influence on Purchase Intention, with a beta coefficient (β) of 0.647 and a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$).

Therefore, the magnitude of the indirect effect is calculated as follows:

$$0.680 \times 0.647 = 0.439$$

Based on this result, H_2 is accepted, indicating that the Brand Ambassador has an indirect influence on Purchase Intention, mediated by Brand Image.

Path Coefficients of Brand Ambassador on Brand Image and Purchase Intention, with Brand Image as a Mediating Variable

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Direct Effect (DE)} &= XY \\ &= 0,530 \\ \text{Indirect Effect (IE)} &= ZX \times YZ \\ &= 0,680 \times 0,647 \\ &= 0.439 \\ \text{Total Effect (TE)} &= XY + (ZX \times YZ) \\ &= 0,530 + 0.439 \\ &= 0.969 \end{aligned}$$

DISCUSSION

Overall, this study was conducted to examine both the direct and indirect influence of **brand ambassadors** on **purchase intention**. The **brand ambassador** variable recorded the highest result on the **appeal** dimension. This indicates that **NCT Dream** possesses strong visual or physical appeal, which has the most significant influence, especially among younger audiences. The second most influential dimension is **congruence**, suggesting that NCT Dream has relevant knowledge and expertise regarding Somethinc's products. The third is **credibility**, which means that NCT Dream is perceived as convincing and trustworthy, encouraging consumers to purchase and use Somethinc products.

The fourth dimension is **transference**, meaning NCT Dream is effective in promoting Somethinc's products to followers of TikTok @somethincofficial. Lastly, the **power** dimension showed the lowest score among the five, though this does not indicate that power is irrelevant in their role as brand ambassadors. Rather, the appeal, congruence, credibility, and transference dimensions had a stronger influence within the brand ambassador variable.

The **brand image** variable yielded the highest score in the **favorability of brand association** dimension, indicating that Somethinc's products are seen as high-quality and beneficial, continuously offering unique advantages that contribute to a **positive brand image** in the minds of consumers. The second strongest dimension is **strength of brand association**, which is crucial to maintain. The strength of Somethinc's brand depends on how deeply information is processed and retained in consumers' memory. The more deeply consumers reflect on and internalize brand information, the stronger the brand image becomes. The lowest score was found

The Influence of NCT Dream as Brand Ambassadors through Tiktok @Somethincofficial on Brand Image and Consumer Purchase Intention

in the **uniqueness of brand association** dimension, suggesting that Somethinc should develop more distinctive products and features that are difficult for competitors to replicate.

In the **purchase intention** variable, the highest score was found in the **referential intention** dimension. This suggests that Somethinc must maintain its product quality so that consumers consistently recommend it to friends or family. The second highest dimension was **transactional intention**, which highlights the importance of identifying potential buyers and developing appropriate marketing strategies to influence and drive purchases. The third was **preferential intention**, which is essential for understanding consumer preferences and expectations and supporting product development. The lowest score was in the **explorative intention** dimension. This presents an opportunity for Somethinc to build deeper relationships with followers of TikTok @somethincofficial and maintain quality and brand image to secure positive consumer reviews.

The findings of this study indicate that the **brand ambassador** variable has both a direct and indirect influence on **purchase intention**. Based on the calculations, the **direct influence ($\beta = 0.530$)** of brand ambassador on purchase intention is **stronger** than the **indirect influence ($\beta = 0.439$)** mediated by **brand image**, confirming the acceptance of H_3 . These results are consistent with the findings of Molina et al. (2023) and Adingsih & Yunani (2023), both of which also showed that direct effects outweighed indirect effects. This suggests that while brand image mediates the relationship, brand ambassadors can directly influence purchase decisions. The stronger direct influence may be attributed to the fact that the selected brand ambassadors are globally renowned Korean celebrities with highly loyal fan bases. Their popularity generates trust and a strong emotional connection with consumers, prompting quicker responses to product endorsements. Moreover, their lifestyles and positive public images are directly associated with the brand, increasing purchase intention without the need for further persuasion.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- **Brand ambassador** has a **direct influence** on **consumer purchase intention**.
- **Brand ambassador** also has an **indirect influence** on **consumer purchase intention** through **brand image**.
- The **direct influence** of the brand ambassador on purchase intention is **stronger** than the **indirect influence** mediated by brand image.

Suggestions

Future research is recommended to further explore the relationship between **brand ambassador**, **brand image**, and **purchase intention** using different concepts and dimensions. It is also suggested to investigate different objects or contexts beyond those used in this study.

For **Somethinc**, it is advised to enhance a variety of strategies that strengthen both **brand image** and **consumer purchase intention**. These efforts should go beyond promotional content on TikTok @somethincofficial, expanding the range of stimuli that drive consumer interest and increase purchase intention.

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